

Supplementary materials: Results at NUTS 3 level

Wind power potential in low environmental sensitivity areas of Spain: a regional assessment*

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Summary of main hypotheses:

- The environmental sensitivity assessment is based on the ISA index performed by MITECO ([link](#)). Here, the potential in “Low sensitivity” areas, corresponding to the lowest of the five defined ISA classes, is estimated. However, low sensitivity does not imply that an environmental impact assessment is unnecessary for wind farm development. Wind farms may also be located in other ISA classes following a preliminary environmental impact assessment.
- Wind resource from New European Wind Atlas (NEWA), wind speed at 100 m height, year 2013.
- Software: [atlite](#)
- Wind power density: 10 MW/km²
- Power curve from wind turbine model: Vestas V112 3MW h100.
- Correction factor to account for wind farm losses: 0.93
- Capacity factor threshold: 0.285 (~2500 equiv. hours)

NUTS 3 regions		
ES111 (A Coruña)	ES413 (León)	ES514 (Tarragona)
ES112 (Lugo)	ES414 (Palencia)	ES521 (Alicante/Alacant)
ES113 (Ourense)	ES415 (Salamanca)	ES522 (Castellón/Castelló)
ES114 (Pontevedra)	ES416 (Segovia)	ES523 (Valencia/València)
ES120 (Asturias)	ES417 (Soria)	ES531 (Eivissa y Formentera)
ES130 (Cantabria)	ES418 (Valladolid)	ES532 (Mallorca)
ES211 (Áraba/Álava)	ES419 (Zamora)	ES533 (Menorca)
ES212 (Gipuzkoa)	ES421 (Albacete)	ES611 (Almería)
ES213 (Bizkaia)	ES422 (Ciudad Real)	ES612 (Cádiz)
ES220 (Navarra)	ES423 (Cuenca)	ES613 (Córdoba)
ES230 (La Rioja)	ES424 (Guadalajara)	ES614 (Granada)
ES241 (Huesca)	ES425 (Toledo)	ES615 (Huelva)
ES242 (Teruel)	ES431 (Badajoz)	ES616 (Jaén)
ES243 (Zaragoza)	ES432 (Cáceres)	ES617 (Málaga)
ES300 (Madrid)	ES511 (Barcelona)	ES618 (Sevilla)
ES411 (Ávila)	ES512 (Girona)	ES620 (Murcia)
ES412 (Burgos)	ES513 (Lleida)	

A Coruña (ES111)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 10.59%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 8.39 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Lugo (ES112)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 18.41%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 18.12 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Ourense (ES113)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 5.67%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 4.11 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Pontevedra (ES114)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 5.87%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 2.63 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Asturias (ES120)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 6.11%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 6.48 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Cantabria (ES130)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 10.56%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 5.60 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Araba/Álava (ES211)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 6.80%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 2.07 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Gipuzkoa (ES212)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 18.18%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 3.59 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Bizkaia (ES213)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 10.75%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 2.38 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Navarra (ES220)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 14.77%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 15.36 GW** could be installed in these areas.

La Rioja (ES230)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 13.35%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 6.73 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Huesca (ES241)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 5.62%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 8.78 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Teruel (ES242)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 5.31%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 7.87 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Zaragoza (ES243)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 14.87%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 25.68 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Madrid (ES300)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 5.87%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 4.72 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Ávila (ES411)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 5.68%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 4.58 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Burgos (ES412)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 29.52%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 42.14 GW** could be installed in these areas.

León (ES413)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 4.28%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 6.67 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Palencia (ES414)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 34.06%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 27.47 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Salamanca (ES415)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 5.06%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 6.25 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Segovia (ES416)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 6.53%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 4.52 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Soria (ES417)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 24.94%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 25.67 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Valladolid (ES418)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 26.13%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 21.18 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Zamora (ES419)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 13.17%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 13.88 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Albacete (ES421)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 21.15%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 31.58 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Ciudad Real (ES422)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 0.92%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 1.82 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Cuenca (ES423)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 31.06%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 53.24 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Guadalajara (ES424)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 17.57%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 21.41 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Toledo (ES425)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 4.42%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 6.78 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Badajoz (ES431)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 1.59%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 3.45 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Cáceres (ES432)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 0.28%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 0.56 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Barcelona (ES511)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 1.51%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 1.17 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Girona (ES512)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 1.16%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 0.69 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Lleida (ES513)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 5.34%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 6.49 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Tarragona (ES514)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 7.34%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 4.62 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Alicante/Alacant (ES521)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 1.92%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 1.11 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Castellón/Castelló (ES522)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 1.94%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 1.29 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Valencia/València (ES523)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 0.81%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 0.88 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Eivissa y Formentera (ES531)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 24.64%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 1.58 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Mallorca (ES532)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 5.38%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 1.95 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Menorca (ES533)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 7.02%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 0.48 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Almería (ES611)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 12.34%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 10.81 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Cádiz (ES612)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND:** 1.70% of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY:** 1.26 GW could be installed in these areas.

Córdoba (ES613)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 0.00%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 0.00 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Granada (ES614)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 3.82%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 4.83 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Huelva (ES615)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 2.54%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 2.57 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Jaén (ES616)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 0.50%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 0.67 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Málaga (ES617)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 9.43%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 6.89 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Sevilla (ES618)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 4.98%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 6.98 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Murcia (ES620)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 7.47%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 8.44 GW** could be installed in these areas.

Venn's diagrams

